

TECHNOLOGIES OF FORMATION OF ECONOMIC CONCEPTS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article discusses the technologies of formation of economic concepts in preschoolers, discusses such concepts as monetary relations, wealth, the market and its types, national wealth, labor.

Keywords: money, wealth, market, national wealth, cocktail, bank, plastic card, economy, property attitude.

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ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ПОНЯТИЙ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Abstract: В данной статье рассматриваются технологии формирования экономических понятий у дошкольников, рассматриваются такие понятия, как денежные отношения, богатство, рынок и его виды, национальное богатство, труд..

Keywords: деньги, богатство, рынок, национальное богатство, банк, пластиковая карта, экономика, имущественные отношения

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA IQTISODIY TUSHUNCHALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYALARI

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda iqtisodiy tushunchalarni shakllantirish texnologiyalari haqida fikr yuritilgan bo'lib, pul munosabatlari, boylik, bozor va uning turlari, milliy boylik, mehnat kabi tushunchalar haqida fikr yuritilgan...

Keywords: pul, boylik, bozor, milliy boylik, mehnat, bank, plastik kartochka, iqtisod, mulkiy munosabat.

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Economic Education focuses on putting the economic activity of a person into a certain system, explaining his activities in economic conditions. Economic Education is necessary, first of all, to start with the family. And one of its prerequisites is the attitude towards money in the family. A.S.Makarenko in his book "for parents" emphasizes three attitudes towards money. At the same time, the first head of the family says: "there is an increase in naughty everywhere, money glows in all children's pockets," and the second head of the family thinks: "adults are obsessed only with counting money, children are brought up far from such naughty things." The head of the third family - an accountant - expresses his opinion on this issue: "a family is a farm, money comes and is spent. Once there is money, there must be order, whoever has stolen the money, the waterfall can make expenses. Now is the moment to teach children to spend money."

A.S.The very fact that Makarenko called the family of an economically literate accountant "the benchmark family" also shows how necessary this issue is.[3] in a market economy, this need is getting stronger.

The upbringing of the child and the result of it, personal as well as Social Interest, are of importance. Good upbringing not only brings joy, happiness, spiritual and economic wealth to the family, but also benefits for society, and therefore has economic, political-spiritual significance.

Great economist J.M.As Keynes says, the world is ruled by politicians and economists. And important political issues arise from economic issues and problems. [4] hence, all major problems go back to economics.

Each country, as long as society sets a goal for itself, strives for its implementation. This work becomes the idea that the thought, intention, purpose of action is ultimately formed as the main important principle of the worldview.

And the basis of the idea of national independence is an economic idea. The path that corresponds in all respects to the interests of all residents of Uzbekistan, which can be a guarantee for them to live a decent life, ensuring the development of national traditions and culture, the revival of spiritual, moral values, is the path to a socially oriented market economy. The purpose of our choice or, in other words, the economic idea that we set ourselves "the ultimate goal is to build a strong democratic legal state and civil society with a socially oriented stable market economy, an open foreign policy" [5]

Such a ultimate goal is aimed at creating an economic idea and, first of all, a comfortable living environment for the benefit of the people, which is being implemented for its implementation.

After all, from historical data it is clear that our great ancestors put forward many ideas about economics and economic education and upbringing. Because economics plays an important role in the life of everyone, every family, community

and society. He determines not only the life of a person today, but also his future. After all, it was not for nothing that our ring uttered the wisdom "First economics, then politics." Hence, the development of economic thinking in society is of great importance.

The formation of the first economic concepts in kindergarten is envisaged to acquaint children of the middle group with six different economic concepts (economy, labor, wealth, property relations, market, money).

I. Economics is life. To form their vision of living by giving children Economic Insights. The presence of vital needs necessary for human survival, the need for dress, nutrition, play, the need for Labor. The relationship of two types of needs with each other. Conditions for living.

II. Production. Labor. The fact that Labor is the main activity of production in a person's life. Personal labor is Labor, the result of which is labor. The fact that the labor force is focused on the labor of a person. "If Labor comes from wealth, marriage would be beauty". Physical and mental labor. Weapons of Labor. Attitude to work.

III. National wealth. The wealth of a particular society, nation and Elat, created by the work of generations. Creation, use and re-renewal of national wealth. Analysis of cases of ancient professions in Central Asia, causing the disappearance of old ones of new professions. Folk masters who created real samples of art in the field of architecture, crafts. Two sources in the creation of national wealth: 1. The product of Labor. 2. The gift of nature.

IV. Property relations. What is ownership? Forms of ownership: a) state property; B) personal property. Three indispensable resources in mastering ownership:

1. Ownership of property.
2. Take advantage of the property.
3. Sale, inheritance, preservation, reproduction of property

V. Market. The market is the place where the seller and the buyer behave. Market participants: A) seller; B) buyer.

A seller is a person who sells his products. A buyer is a person who buys products from the market in order to satisfy his needs in his life.

Market types: A) peasant market; B) market selling clothing;

C) a market that sells consumption (food). Their difference from each other. Trade carried out in the market. Who is a trader? Its moral qualities are: A) honesty, B) honesty, C) loyalty (business acumen), D) thinking of the interests of the people.

Store. The difference of the store from the market. Types of store. The importance of service to those of trade (buying and selling).

VI. Money. Money is the main means of circulation, through which all products, services are exchanged. Pavdo of money. The development of a person's need for money. Work (function) in which money is performed: A) means of circulation; B) means of accumulation. The value of money. National monetary unit. Save and save money.

VIII. Plastik kartočka. What is a plastic card? The convenience of a plastic card. Determination of the amount of funds on a plastic card. Personal code put on a plastic card. Advantages of uzc card. Measures that must be taken when a plastic card is lost.

IX. Product. Human need for items. Raw materials. The transformation of the product of Labor into a product (commodity). The exchange of a product on the market for a product or money. Product and its quality. The nature of human satisfaction of each product. Labor spent on the production of products. Working time. The place of work is the dependence and influence of the quality of Labor on the quality of products.

The first economic concepts in kindergarten preparation the content of familiarization of children of the group with 12 different economic concepts (economics, labor, family, society, communication, spirituality, maintenance of rules and order, management, trade, money, products) is given.

The main tool in the implementation of the technology for the formation of the first economic concepts is such activities and games as "acquaintance with the environment", "formation of elementary mathematical representations".

In conclusion, on the basis of the first system of economic concepts and activities that form the imagination, children get acquainted with such basic concepts as economics, labor, family, society, wealth, property relations, trade, market, money, products and get an idea of their essence. In preschool organizations, children are introduced to the material world surrounding them (clothes, equipment, food), nature (living, inanimate), society, changes in it, social events, (labor of people, the result of them). It is in the process of training of such content that the first economic concepts are formed in children, and about the concepts of quantity, size, multiplicity, space "are acquired in the training of the formation of elementary mathematical representations. When organizing classes, it is necessary to take into account the age, nature, living conditions of the child, pay special attention to the law of going up close-Far, From Concrete-to abstract, and, of course, to the continuity of education and upbringing.

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